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Flavodiiron Protein Activity Outcompetes Cyclic Electron Transport When Expressed in Angiosperm *Nicotiana tabacum*

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ABSTRACT

In conditions of excess illumination, alternative electron transport pathways in the thylakoid membranes protect the photosynthetic apparatus against damage from eventual over-reduction. Two main pathways downstream of photosystem I (PSI) enable alternative electron flow, mitigating PSI acceptor-side limitation, while contributing to ATP biosynthesis without reducing NADP⁺ to NADPH: cyclic electron transport (CET) and pseudo-cyclic electron transport (PCET). Flavodiiron proteins (FLV) are crucial enzymes in PCET, found in all photosynthetic organisms but lost during the evolution of angiosperms. The absence of FLV coding sequences in angiosperm genomes raises intriguing questions about their role and function in photosynthetic organisms. Previous studies utilizing heterologous expression have already demonstrated that FLV can indeed function in angiosperms. In this study, *Physcomitrium patens* FLVA and FLVB coding sequences were stably expressed in wild-type *Nicotiana tabacum*, a model crop species. Transgenic lines exhibited significantly increased PCET rates, with FLV-dependent electron transport competing for electrons with CET, particularly under sudden increases in light intensity that limited acceptor-side limitation. These findings indicate that heterologously expressed FLVs are not only active but can also play a critical role in protecting from over-reduction the photosynthetic apparatus of *Nicotiana tabacum* under fluctuating light conditions.

1 | Introduction

Photosynthetic organisms utilize sunlight to drive electron transfer from water to NADP⁺, producing NADPH, through the activity of two photosystems (PSII and PSI). This process also generates a transmembrane electrochemical gradient, leading to

ATP synthesis. Together, NADPH and ATP sustain carbon dioxide (CO₂) fixation and several other metabolic reactions (Stirbet et al. 2020).

In natural environments, plants live in dynamic conditions, including dark-to-light transitions, variable light intensities,

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and heterogeneous water and nutrient supply. These factors can disrupt the balance between excitation energy availability and the utilization of photosynthesis end-products, potentially leading to over-reduction of the electron transport chain. In the worst-case scenario, excess electrons may react with oxygen, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can cause irreversible damage to the photosynthetic apparatus (Joliot and Johnson 2011). Mechanisms regulating photosynthesis are crucial to respond to such imbalances, with a major impact on photosynthetic efficiency. Optimizing these mechanisms can also represent a potential strategy to enhance biomass accumulation under field conditions (Kromdijk et al. 2016; De Souza et al. 2022).

Photosynthetic organisms evolved various regulatory mechanisms, including non-photochemical quenching (NPQ), cyclic electron flow (CEF), and pseudo-cyclic electron flow (PCEF). CEF and PCEF operate downstream of PSI, decoupling ATP synthesis from NADPH production and protecting PSI from over-reduction (Alboresi, Storti, and Morosinotto 2019; Ruban and Wilson 2021; Leister 2023).

The two known CEF mechanisms recycle electrons from ferredoxin (Fd) back to the plastoquinone (PQ) pool. The first is mediated by the chloroplast NADPH dehydrogenase-like (NDH) complex (Joliot and Johnson 2011) while the second involves the PGR5/PGRL1 system, which facilitates electron transport from PSI back to the PQ pool (Munekage et al. 2002; DalCorso et al. 2008). Although PGR5 and PGRL1 proteins are clearly involved in regulating CEF (Munekage et al. 2002; Johnson et al. 2014), the precise mechanism by which the electrons are transferred from PSI acceptors to the PQ pool remains under debate (Nawrocki et al. 2019).

PCEF keeps PSI in an oxidized state by transferring P700-derived electrons to molecular oxygen, converting it into H₂O (Messant et al. 2021). Since the electrons originate from H₂O by the activity of the PSII oxygen-evolving complex and ultimately reduce oxygen to water through PCEF, this process is also often termed the “water–water cycle.” PCEF contributes to ΔpH generation but does not support NADPH synthesis and is mediated by two distinct mechanisms: the Mehler reaction and flavodiiron proteins (FLVs).

Mehler reaction detoxifies the superoxide anion produced in PSI when molecular oxygen reacts with electrons from Fd or Fe-S clusters (Foyer and Hanke 2022). Superoxide is first converted into hydrogen peroxide by superoxide dismutase and subsequently scavenged into water molecules by ascorbate-peroxidase (Asada 2000).

In the stroma, FLVs accept electrons downstream of PSI to reduce molecular oxygen into H₂O. These proteins belong to the multigenic flavodiiron protein (FDP) family, found across a diverse range of organisms (Folgosa et al. 2018). In photosynthetic organisms, FLVs consist of three functional domains: an N-terminal metallo-β-lactamase with a diiron-binding center, followed by a domain able to interact with a flavin mononucleotide (FMN) and a final C-terminal domain with NADPH:flavin oxidoreductase activity (Folgosa et al. 2018; Alboresi, Storti, Cendron, and Morosinotto 2019; Beraldo et al. 2024).

FLVs function as safety valves for PSI over-reduction in cyanobacteria (Allahverdiyeva et al. 2013), algae (Chaux et al. 2017; Shimakawa et al. 2022), non-vascular plants (Gerotto et al. 2016; Shimakawa et al. 2017) and gymnosperms (Ilík et al. 2017; Bag et al. 2023). In these organisms, they play a critical role during dark-to-light transitions and under fluctuating light intensities when the Calvin-Benson cycle is inactive and thus cannot fully utilize the reducing equivalents produced by the linear electron transport chain (Storti, Segalla, et al. 2020). Their activity is not detectable during steady-state photosynthesis, even though their presence may still generate an impact (Traverso et al. 2025).

Mutant lines deficient in FLV accumulation in different species exhibit pronounced light sensitivity when exposed to light fluctuations, highlighting the critical role of FLVs in photoprotection across various organisms (Jokel et al. 2015; Gerotto et al. 2016; Shimakawa et al. 2017). Despite this general role, FLVs were lost during angiosperm evolution (Hanawa et al. 2017; Ilík et al. 2017) and are also absent in some eukaryotic algae, such as diatoms (Shimakawa et al. 2019).

One possible reason why angiosperms have not conserved FLVs may be attributed to the fact that FLV catalyzes a futile reaction that dissipates electrons, which could be detrimental for efficiency in limiting light conditions. This is consistent with the observation that at least if strongly over-expressed, FLV activity can become detrimental (Traverso et al. 2025). This will be accompanied by the increased efficiency in angiosperms of other electron sinks such as the cyclic electron pathway (Yamamoto et al. 2016), the Calvin-Benson cycle, and photorespiration (Hanawa et al. 2017; Shikanai and Yamamoto 2017) that could have made the FLV activity less essential and thus dispensable.

Attempts to express heterologous FLV genes from cyanobacteria or the moss *Physcomitrium patens* in angiosperms have demonstrated that these proteins can function as electron acceptors downstream of PSI (Yamamoto et al. 2016; Gómez et al. 2018; Wada et al. 2018). In wild-type *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Oryza sativa*, PSI is limited on the acceptor side upon light activation and following sudden increases in light intensity. However, expression of *P. patens* FLVA and FLVB in wild-type plants reduces this limitation, demonstrating that the heterologously expressed proteins are active and contribute to PCEF rates under fluctuating light conditions (Yamamoto et al. 2016; Wada et al. 2018). Similarly, *Nicotiana tabacum* lines expressing cyanobacterial *Flv1-Flv3* exhibit faster responses during dark-to-light transitions (Gómez et al. 2018). Moreover, expression of *P. patens* FLVs has been shown to partially rescue the phenotypes of CEF knock-out lines (Yamamoto et al. 2016; Wada et al. 2018). No measurable FLV activity was instead detected during steady-state photosynthesis, and their expression does not significantly impact carbon fixation under constant illumination, suggesting that the contribution of PCEF under steady-state conditions is negligible (Yamamoto et al. 2016; Wada et al. 2018). While these studies confirm that FLVs are active when expressed heterologously in angiosperms and can act as alternative electron sinks and contribute to the response to light fluctuations, several important questions remain without an answer. A key unresolved issue is whether FLVs provide a measurable advantage in photosynthetic efficiency or stress tolerance under conditions such as fluctuating light, prolonged high-light exposure, or rapid dark-to-light transitions.

To address this point, we expressed *P. patens* *FLVA-FLVB* in WT *N. tabacum*. Our results confirm not only that FLVs are active in this species and capable of supporting a high flow of electrons but also that the transport rates are comparable to those observed in the native organism *P. patens* (Gerotto et al. 2016; Traverso et al. 2025). We also quantified the electron flow in WT and FLV-expressing lines, discovering how FLV actively oxidizes P700 alternatively to CEF, supporting the hypothesis that CEF compensates for the absence of FLVs in angiosperms. Additionally, we report for the first time that, by mitigating PSI acceptor-side limitation, PCEF significantly enhances photoprotection upon exposure to light fluctuations.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Plant Material and Growth Conditions

Nicotiana tabacum cv. Samsung NN, WT, and FLV-expressing plants were sowed on watered filter paper, and after germination, plantlets were transferred to germinators for 1 week; finally, they were planted into single pots for all the analyses. Plants were grown in a growth chamber at 25°C, 45%–65% air humidity under a photoperiod of 16-h day (100 μmol m⁻²s⁻¹) and 8-h night. To test photosynthetic efficiency under fluctuating light conditions, 3-week-old plants were positioned under an LED lamp (Photon System Instruments; SL 3500) and subjected to 4.5 min at 50 μmol m⁻²s⁻¹ followed by 30 s at 1000 μmol m⁻²s⁻¹. The photoperiod was 16-h of fluctuating light and 8-h night. To increase the stress related to light fluctuation, this treatment was performed in a growth chamber at 16°C.

Physcomitrium patens ssp. Gransden WT and *flv* KO (Gerotto et al. 2016). All plants were routinely propagated as previously described on PpNH₄ rich medium at 24°C under long-day conditions (16/8 h day/night). For photosynthetic measurements and for plant growth quantification, the individual lines were cultivated photoautotrophically on PpNO₃ minimal medium (Ashton et al. 1979; Storti et al. 2019).

2.2 | Molecular Cloning and Plant Transformation

The introduction of the two *P. patens* *FLVA* and *FLVB* genes in *N. tabacum* was achieved by expressing the *FLVA-2A-FLVB* sequence (Yamamoto et al. 2016) under the control of the 35S constitutive promoter.

FLVA-2A-FLVB gene (4182 bp) was subcloned in pDONR221 and then transferred into the pBinAR expression vector (Hofgen and Willmitzer 1988) using the Gateway cloning system to obtain pBinAr-35S::*FLVA-2A-FLVB* vector. *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain LBA4404 was used for the stable transformation of *N. tabacum* plants (Fisher and Guiltinan 1995). Young, healthy, and undamaged leaves were collected from in vitro grown WT tobacco plants and soaked in a suspension of *A. tumefaciens* cells (OD₆₀₀ ~0.8) in MS salts without vitamins (4.3 g L⁻¹), sucrose (30 g L⁻¹), 6-BAP (1 mg L⁻¹) and Gamborg B5 medium (1 mL L⁻¹ of 1000× stock solution) for 10 min to allow the infection cycle.

Leaves were then placed on TAB1 co-cultivation medium (MS salts with vitamins 4.4 g L⁻¹, sucrose 30 g L⁻¹, 6-BAP 1 mg L⁻¹, IAA 0.2 mg L⁻¹, plant agar 5 g L⁻¹, pH 5.7) and incubated in the dark at 23°C for 48 h. Leaves were then transferred to plates containing TAB2 medium (TAB1 medium supplemented with kanamycin 200 mg L⁻¹ and cefotaxime 500 mg L⁻¹) and incubated at 23°C with a 16/8 h light/dark photoperiod. The TAB2 medium was refreshed every 15 days until callus formation occurred. Once shoots of 1–3 cm in length emerged from the callus masses, independent clones were cut off and placed in Magenta boxes containing TAB3 medium (MS salts with vitamins 4.4 g L⁻¹, sucrose 30 g L⁻¹, plant agar 6 g L⁻¹, kanamycin 200 mg L⁻¹ and cefotaxime 500 mg L⁻¹, pH 5.7) for rooting. After ~20 days, plants were analyzed by PCR on genomic DNA to confirm the presence of the transgene and then transferred to soil. The selected T₀ plants were self-crossed to obtain the corresponding T₁ and T₂ lines. Segregation analysis of the transgene was conducted by sowing pre-sterilized T₂ seeds in MS 1/2 medium supplemented with kanamycin 200 mg L⁻¹ (Figure S2). The plates were incubated in a growth chamber at 25°C (16/8 h light/dark photoperiod) for 15 days, after which germinated plants, resistant to kanamycin selection, showed green developed cotyledons.

2.3 | Gene Expression Analysis

RNA was purified from leaf disks with TRI Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich) and used as a template for cDNA synthesis to verify *FLVA*, *FLVB*, and *H2A* expression. The primers used for PCR are the following: *FLVA*f: 5'-GATGCCCCGGGATGGAGACGATGT TGGTG-3', *FLVA*r: 5'-CACCTAACATCTGCCTCCT-3', *FLVB*f: 5'-CTGTCAAAGCCAAGCAACCC-3', *FLVB*r: 5'-AGGACTT CCATTTGCCCCAG-3', *H2A*f: 5'-GAGTTACCATCGCAAGC GGA-3', and *H2A*r: 5'-ATGCCTTCTCCTCAGCTGCA-3'.

2.4 | Immunoblot Analysis

Total extracts were obtained by grinding leaf disks in 150 μL sample buffer (50 mM TRIS pH 6.8, 100 mM DTT, 2% SDS, and 10% glycerol) and centrifuged at 13,000 g. An aliquot of the supernatant was used for chlorophyll extraction in acetone 80%. Chlorophyll content was quantified at the spectrophotometer (Cary Series UV-Vis, Agilent Technologies) applying the formula below (Porra et al. 1989):

$$\text{Chls}_{a+b} (\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}) = 17.76 \times A_{646.6} + 7.34 \times A_{663.6}$$

The supernatant was incubated at 100°C for 1 min before loading into SDS/PAGE. The quantity of samples to load was estimated in terms of equivalents of chlorophyll amount. For immunoblotting analysis, after SDS/PAGE, proteins were transferred to nitrocellulose membranes (Pall Corporation) and hybridized with specific commercial antibodies (PSAA, Agrisera, catalog numbers AS06 172) and homemade polyclonal antibodies (PsaD, γATPase, Cyt f, PsbS, D2, NDH-H, RuBisCO, and LHCI) and custom-made anti-*FLVB*. The proteins were detected with alkaline phosphatase-conjugated secondary antibody and colorimetric assay.

Further validation of FLV expression in *N. tabacum* transgenic clones was performed through immunoblot analysis, which detected the accumulation of *P. patens* FLVB in multiple lines. Among the transgenic *N. tabacum* lines showing positive results in both P700 oxidation kinetics and FLV protein accumulation, clones #1, #7, and #8 were selected for propagation to F2 generation and further investigations (Table S1).

RT-PCR showed that both FLVA and FLVB genes were expressed in these lines (Figure 1A). Immunoblot analysis confirmed that the accumulation level of FLVB protein was

FIGURE 1 | FLV expression and Immunoblot analysis of photosynthesis-related proteins in *N. tabacum* lines. (A) The expression of FLVA and FLVB was verified via RT-PCR, H2A histone served as the endogenous control. (B) Immunoblot analysis was performed to detect photosynthesis related proteins in both wild-type (WT) and transgenic lines of *N. tabacum* expressing FLVA-2A-FLVB. The proteins analyzed included FLVB, RuBisCO, γ -ATPase, PSAA, PSAD, D2, LHCII, PsbS, Cyt-f, and NDH-H. The detection was carried out using different chlorophyll equivalents as follows: 1 \times is equivalent to 2 μ g of chlorophylls for the detection of FLVB, γ -ATPase, PSAA, PSAD, D2, PsbS, Cyt-f, and NDH-H. 1 \times is equivalent to 0.2 μ g of chlorophylls for the detection of RuBisCO and LHCII. The amounts 0.5 \times and 2 \times represent half and twice the amount of 1 \times , respectively.

comparable among the selected lines (Figure 1B). To assess whether the expression of FLV proteins impacted the composition of photosynthetic machinery in transgenic *N. tabacum* lines, we analyzed the content of key proteins associated with photosystems and electron transport. The levels of proteins constituting PSII (D2) and PSI (PSAA and PSAD) as well as major antenna proteins (LHCII) showed no evident alterations in FLV transgenic lines as compared to WT. The abundance of Cyt *f* and γ -ATPase also did not significantly change in FLV lines in respect to WT (Figure 1B). The accumulation of PsbS, the key activator of non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) of chlorophyll fluorescence at the level of PSII, also remained unchanged between WT and FLV lines (Figure 1B). No significant changes in RuBisCO enzyme or the NDH-H subunit were detected between WT and FLV lines as well (Figure 1B). Overall, FLVs expression, thus, had no major alterations on the composition of the *N. tabacum* photosynthetic apparatus.

As the three independent lines displayed consistent behavior across all analyses, from here on the overall average data are presented for clarity.

To validate FLV activity and confirm the initial screening results (Figure S1), we employed a quantitative protocol to determine the fraction of oxidized P700 (P700⁺) relative to the total amount of photo-oxidizable P700. To this aim, plants were exposed to repetitive 1-s saturating pulses (rSPs) over a background of moderate light intensity between (Shimakawa and Miyake 2018; Furutani et al. 2022) (Figures 2A and S2A). In WT plants, PSI was oxidized at only 20% of its maximum capacity, while in FLV lines, 80% of PSI reaction centers were kept in an oxidized state during the last 1-s treatment (Figures 2B and S2B). This result confirmed that *P. patens* FLVs expressed in *N. tabacum* were actively oxidizing P700.

3.2 | FLV Expression Enhances the Response of *N. tabacum* to Fluctuating Light Conditions

In *P. patens* plants, FLV activity was indispensable in dark-to-light transitions and after a sudden increase in incident illumination (Gerotto et al. 2016; Storti, Segalla, et al. 2020). Consistent results were also found in all FLV-expressing organisms (Allahverdiyeva et al. 2013; Chaux et al. 2017; Shimakawa et al. 2017). Therefore, we challenged *N. tabacum* plants with three cycles of limiting (low) and saturating (high) light intensities, monitoring different photosynthetic parameters (Figures 3 and S3).

All genotypes showed the same initial F_v/F_m values (WT = 0.78 \pm 0.01; FLV lines = 0.77 \pm 0.01). During the initial transition from darkness to low light, WT plants had low PSI and PSII yields (respectively Y(I) and Y(II)) that recovered after a few minutes of illumination (Figure 3A,D). While this drop was visible in dark-adapted plants, it was absent in the following low-to-high light cycles (Figure S3), when samples were already light-adapted. Interestingly, FLV-expressing lines showed higher Y(I) and Y(II) with respect to WT in this dark-to-low light transition (Figure 3A,D). Upon exposure to a stronger light, after 5 min in low light, both Y(I) and Y(II) strongly decreased to \sim 0.1, as a result of the saturation of photosystem photochemical capacity (Figure 3A,D).

FIGURE 2 | Oxidized P700 fraction in *Nicotiana tabacum* plants. (A) Comparison between wild-type (WT) and the FLV-expressing lines, the kinetics of oxidized P700 (P700⁺) during illumination with a short-pulse light (SP: $\sim 2000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 1 s). WT plants (black) and FLV-expressing lines (green) were subjected to SP in the presence of a background light of $\sim 70 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The relative P700⁺ amount is normalized to Pm, which represents the maximum oxidation level of P700. Standard deviation is indicated as a shadow. (B) P700 oxidation index shown as percentage of P700⁺ over the total P700. The integration of the P700⁺ was calculated as the sum of relative P700⁺ values every 0.3 ms during SP illumination, which was then divided by the maximum integrated area. WT, $n = 4 \pm \text{SD}$. FLV, $n = 11 \pm \text{SD}$. A red asterisk indicates statistical significance (one-way ANOVA).

FIGURE 3 | Effect of *P. patens* FLVs on photosynthetic parameters of *N. tabacum*. Photosynthetic efficiency was monitored during fluctuating light cycles for WT plants (black squares) and FLV-expressing lines (green circles): Y(I) (A), Y(NA) (B), Y(ND) (C), Y(II) (D), Y(NPQ) (E), and 1-qL (F). At time 0, after 40 min of dark adaptation, plants were treated with low actinic light ($\sim 60 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; yellow bars) for 5 min followed by saturating actinic light ($\sim 1600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; orange bars) for 1 min. This cycle was repeated two more times as shown in Figure S3. Data are averages $\pm \text{SD}$, with statistical significance indicated by red asterisks ($p < 0.01$, one-way ANOVA). WT plants: $n = 7$; FLV lines: $n = 17$.

In FLV-expressing lines, there were significant differences in the dark-to-light and low-to-high light transitions (Figure 3). The cycle was applied consecutively three times (Figure S3).

During the third cycle, Y(I) values during the low light period were significantly higher in FLV lines (~ 0.8) than in WT plants (~ 0.73) (Figure S3).

FIGURE 5 | Photosynthetic electron transport in *N. tabacum* WT and FLV-expressing lines. (A) Total photosynthetic ETR measured in WT (black squares) and FLV-expressing lines (green circles) at $940\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ actinic light, calculated from electrochromic shift signal. (B) Cyclic electron transport rate measured in the same samples treated with the PSII inhibitor 3-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethyl urea (DCMU). Data represent average values \pm SD, $n=6$ for the WT, $n=17$ for FLV lines. Differences between WT and mutant plants were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.01$).

ECS signals (Figures S6 and 6A) and similar levels of *pmf* (Figures S6 and 6C). Likewise, no significant differences were observed in proton conductance (gH^+), used as an estimate of ATP synthase activity and proton dissipation efficiency (Figure 6D). This suggests that at steady state, photosynthesis activity is highly similar in WT and FLV-expressing lines (Figure 6). Interestingly, a similar picture emerges in measurements after a few seconds of illumination (Figure S6) showing that FLV does not impact overall *pmf* generation nor ATP synthase activity.

To further dissect the impact of FLVs in ETR, we treated leaf disks with the PSII inhibitor, 3-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethyl urea (DCMU), to suppress linear electron flow and thus specifically quantify CET around PSI (Figures 5B and S5). The inhibitor induced a major reduction in ECS signals (Figure 6B) and *pmf* (Figure 6C) in both WT and FLV-expressing lines, but no significant difference was detected between the two genotypes. Also, no significant difference in gH^+ between treated and untreated *N. tabacum* plants and between genotypes was observed (Figure 6D).

3.4 | FLV Expression Increases Tolerance to Fluctuating Light During Growth

To elucidate the impact of FLVs on photosynthetic activity during plant growth, WT and FLV-expressing lines of *N. tabacum* were grown under constant control light intensity (CL) and the maximum efficiency of PSII and PSI was monitored as F_v/F_m and P_m (the maximal change in the P700 signal), respectively (Figures 7 and S7). WT and FLV-expressing lines showed similar values both at the level of P_m (Figure 7A) and F_v/F_m (Figure 7B).

When plants were exposed to fluctuating light conditions (FL; 4.5 min at $50\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ followed by 30 s at $1000\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$), all genotypes showed reduced P_m and F_v/F_m values compared to their CL-grown counterparts (Figure 7). However, FLV

expressing lines retained significantly higher P_m and F_v/F_m values as compared to WT plants (Figure 7), suggesting a photoprotective effect of FLV during plant growth, making plants more tolerant to light fluctuations.

4 | Discussion

4.1 | FLV Has an Intrinsic Ability to Provide Fast Activation of Electron Transport

Upon a sudden increase in light intensity, the photosynthetic electron transport chain reacts rapidly, quickly producing NADPH and ATP. However, the metabolic pathways that consume these energy carriers, such as the Calvin-Benson cycle, require more time to adjust. This mismatch creates an electron accumulation in the transport chain, particularly downstream of PSI and PSII. This over-reduction increases the risk of reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation, which can cause oxidative stress and photodamage to key components like PSI (Allahverdiyeva et al. 2013; Gerotto et al. 2016; Chaux et al. 2017; Shimakawa et al. 2017; Bag et al. 2023). The photoprotective effect of FLVs derives from their ability to mitigate imbalances caused by the fast increase in electron transport and the slow regulation of energy-consuming metabolic processes. Data from different species support the idea that FLVs are essential during the dark-to-light transition and during a sudden increase in light intensity to avoid PSI over-reduction (Allahverdiyeva et al. 2011; Gerotto et al. 2016; Traverso et al. 2025). Due to its capacity of rapidly accepting electrons from PSI, FLVs effectively prevent acceptor side limitation and consequent damage with a protective role. This function has been conserved during the evolution of photosynthetic organisms since it was consistently observed across diverse species, including cyanobacteria (Allahverdiyeva et al. 2013), eukaryotic algae (Jokel et al. 2015; Chaux et al. 2017; Burlacot et al. 2018) and non-vascular plants (Gerotto et al. 2016;

FIGURE 6 | Impact of DCMU treatment on WT and FLV-expressing lines. (A, B) Electrochromic shift (ECS) signal recorded immediately after light was switched off following 5 min of illumination, in the absence (A) and presence (B) of DCMU. WT is shown in black, and FLV-expressing *N. tabacum* lines in green. (C) Proton motive force (pmf) calculated from ECS data shown in (A) and (B). (D) Proton conductance (gH^+) estimated as the inverse of the time constant ($1/\tau$) from the initial 300ms ECS decay after light-off, based on data in (A) and (B). Data represent mean \pm SD; $n = 5$ for WT, $n = 3$ for FLV clone 1, $n = 4$ for FLV clone 7, and $n = 4$ for FLV clone 8. Statistical differences between WT and transgenic lines were assessed using one-way ANOVA.

Shimakawa et al. 2017; Storti et al. 2019; Storti, Puggioni, et al. 2020; Storti, Segalla, et al. 2020).

In this study, we introduced FLVs from *P. patens* into the model crop *N. tabacum* plants, a species widely used for engineering various aspects of photosynthesis. These efforts have included modifications to non-photochemical quenching (Kromdijk et al. 2016), the Rubisco enzyme (Chen, Riaz, et al. 2023), CO₂-concentrating mechanisms in chloroplasts (Chen, Hojka, et al. 2023) and the regulation of photorespiration (South et al. 2019).

P. patens FLVA/B are successfully expressed and accumulated in *N. tabacum* plants (Figure 1). Their full functionality is confirmed by FLV activity measured at the onset of light activation, as they effectively maintain P700 in a safely oxidized state (Figures 2 and S1) and alleviate PSI acceptor side limitation compared to WT *N. tabacum* (Figure 3B). These effects can be attributed to a significant electron flow toward FLVs, detectable as early as 1s after illumination begins. A comparable transient increase in ETR is observed in WT *P. patens* but is absent

in FLV-depleted moss lines (Figure 5A; Gerotto et al. 2016). In angiosperms, this role of contributing to ETR upon light fluctuations is rather played by CET (Yamori and Shikanai 2016), whose activity is decreased in FLV-expressing lines. This may indicate a stronger CEF activation in the WT compared to FLV-expressing plants.

Interestingly, after 4s of illumination, an inversion is observed whereby WT plants exhibit higher electron transport rates than FLV-expressing lines (Figure 5A). Since ETR is derived from ECS signals reflecting membrane potential, this suggests that the contribution of CEF to proton gradient formation exceeds that of PCEF. These results further underscore the complex interplay and competition between CEF and FLV activities (Hubáček et al. 2024).

WT and FLV-depleted *P. patens* showed comparable electron transport capacity at steady state (Gerotto et al. 2016) where the impact of FLV presence was not detectable. Interestingly, also WT and FLV-expressing *Nicotiana tabacum* steady state ETR are indistinguishable, thus confirming how FLV

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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of fluctuating light on PSI and PSII: Y(I) (A), Y(II) (B), Y(ND) (C), NPQ (D), Y(NA) (E), and 1-qL (F) in the WT (black squares) and three independent lines expressing FLV proteins (green circles for clone 1, blue circles for clone 7 and magenta circles for line 8). At time 0, after 40 min of dark adaptation, plants were treated with low actinic light ($60 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; yellow bars) for 5 min followed by saturating actinic light ($1,600 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; orange bars) for 1 min. This cycle was repeated 2 more times. Data represent average values \pm SD, $n = 7$ for the WT, $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 1, $n = 5$ for FLV lines clone 7 and $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 8. Differences between WT and mutant plants in the saturating/limiting light cycles were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance between WT and all the three FLV-expressing lines ($p < 0.01$). **Figure S4:** *P. patens* FLV repress cyclic electron transport in *N. tabacum* plants. Effect of fluctuating light on ETRI (A), ETRII (B) and ETRI-ETRII (C) as a proxy for cyclic electron transport of WT plants (black squares) and two independent lines expressing FLV proteins (green circles for clone 1, blue circles for clone 7 and magenta circles for line 8). At time 0, after 40 min of dark adaptation, plants were treated with low actinic light ($60 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; yellow bars) for 5 min followed by saturating actinic light ($1,600 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; orange bars) for 1 min. This cycle was repeated 2 more times. Data represent average values \pm SD, $n = 7$ for the WT, $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 1, $n = 5$ for FLV lines clone 7 and $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 8. Differences between WT and mutant plants in the saturating/limiting light cycles were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance between WT and all the three FLV-expressing lines ($p < 0.01$). **Figure S5:** Photosynthetic electron transport in *N. tabacum* WT and FLV-expressing lines. (A) Total photosynthetic ETR measured in WT (black squares) and FLV-expressing lines (green circles for clone 1, blue circles for clone 7 and magenta circles for line 8) at $940 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ actinic light, calculated from electrochromic shift signal. (B) Cyclic electron transport rate measured in the same samples treated with the PSII inhibitor 3-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,1-dimethyl urea (DCMU). Data represent average values \pm SD, $n = 6$ for the WT, $n = 5$ for FLV lines clone 1, $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 7 and $n = 6$ for FLV lines clone 8. Differences between WT and mutant plants were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.01$). **Figure S6:** Impact of FLV expression in *N. tabacum* pmf generation. (A) ECS (Electro-Chromic Shift) signal after the light is switch off after 5 s of illumination (WT in black and FLV-*N. tabacum* in green). (B) Total pmf calculated from ECS data presented in (A). Data represent average values \pm SD, $n = 2$ for the WT, $n = 2$ for FLV lines clone 1, $n = 2$ for FLV lines clone 7 and $n = 2$ for FLV lines clone 8. Differences between WT and mutant plants were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.01$). **Figure S7:** Effect of light regime on PSI and PSII efficiency. Pm (A) and Fv/Fm (B) were measured in dark adapted WT (black) and FLV-expressing lines (FLV clone 1 in green, FLV clone 7 in blue and FLV clone 8 in magenta) grown at different light regimes for 14 days. The left panels show data for plants grown under standard light conditions ($100 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; photoperiod 16 h of light and 8 h of dark; 25°C). The panels on the right show data for plants grown under fluctuating light conditions (4.5 min at $50 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ followed by 30 s at $1000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; photoperiod 16 h of fluctuating light and 8 h of dark; 16°C). Data were recorded for each plant once a day. (A) WT, $n = 3$. FLV, $n = 3$ for clone 1, $n = 3$ for clone 7, $n = 4$ for clone 8 (standard light); WT, $n = 3$. FLV, $n = 2$ for clone 1, $n = 2$ for clone 7, $n = 2$ for clone 8 (fluctuating light). (B) WT, $n = 11$. FLV, $n = 8$ for clone 1, $n = 6$ for clone 7, $n = 11$ for clone 8 (standard light); WT, $n = 7$. FLV, $n = 6$ for clone 1, $n = 6$ for clone 7, $n = 6$ for clone 8 (fluctuating light). Differences between WT and mutant plants were examined by one-way ANOVA; a red asterisk indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.01$). **Table S1:** Analysis of T2 generation of FLV transgenic lines. FLV transgenic lines #1, #7, and #8 were tested for resistance to kanamycin. Resistant lines were then tested for the presence of FLVA gene in the genome and for FLV activity by measurement of redox kinetics of P700 upon dark-to-light transition.